

190 **Table S4.** Hysteresis parameters data (used VSM 3900) of Australasian tektites from South China.

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Sample ID	Type	Sampling Location	$M_s (\times 10^{-4} \text{Am}^2/\text{kg})$	$M_{rs} (\times 10^{-6} \text{Am}^2/\text{kg})$	B_c (mT)	B_{cr} (mT)
MNL-1	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	9.16	28.31	5.80	18.40
MNL-2	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	7.72	34.82	8.05	10.10
MNL-3	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	3.51	13.28	6.39	18.40
MNL-4	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	0.37	8.56	7.63	28.20
MNK-1	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	5.13	31.18	9.01	21.83
MNK-2	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	5.32	26.72	9.67	39.70
MN-Z	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	7.56	31.49	12.12	43.30
MNL-S	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	4.43	48.17	11.09	27.86
MNK-S	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	1.19	18.20	13.93	61.39
HN1-1	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	3.49	9.06	8.41	13.04
HN2-1	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	6.00	41.63	11.12	25.91
HN3-1	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	2.08	6.07	6.41	no data
HN4-1	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	3.79	12.97	5.96	28.21
HN5-1	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	4.90	20.14	8.20	28.21
HN6-1	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	3.16	111.00	15.82	34.00
WCMN	Splash-form	Hainan Province	3.74	12.45	3.97	no data
HNWC-2	Splash-form	Hainan Province	1.65	9.74	4.29	no data
HNWC	Splash-form	Hainan Province	2.43	12.46	11.84	no data
HNCM	Splash-form	Hainan Province	3.72	8.95	6.25	no data
GPZ	Splash-form	Hainan Province	2.75	2.44	2.66	no data
WSD-S	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	0.79	2.85	19.60	no data
GDLZ-S1	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	4.61	16.61	7.54	no data
GDLZ-S2	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	3.68	8.62	8.97	no data
GDLZ-S3	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	2.77	1.83	7.81	no data
ZJDT	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	3.01	6.34	2.42	no data
EC	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	4.26	7.21	3.64	no data
GC	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	5.10	8.81	5.13	no data
GDZJ-S1	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	3.95	8.43	5.92	no data
GDZJ-S4-1	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	2.04	2.03	8.87	no data
GDZJ-S6	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	2.33	6.57	7.91	no data
ZJZW-1	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	1.31	1.56	13.68	no data
ZWC	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	2.61	9.47	8.19	no data
GDMM	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	1.89	5.02	8.27	no data
GXYL-S2	Splash-form	Guangxi Province	2.28	15.10	12.81	no data

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